

Effect of mercury on worsening hypertension outcomes in hypertensive patients exposed to Martapura river water

Efecto del mercurio en el empeoramiento de los resultados de hipertensión en pacientes hipertensos expuestos al agua del río Martapura

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Abstract

Mercury has been reported contaminated waters of Martapura River. Mercury has high levels of toxicity for almost organ systems, including renocardiovascular systems and hypertension as one of the parts of the disease. The mayor aims of the studi to investigate the effect of mercury on worsening hypertension outcomes in hypertensive patients exposed to contamination of the Martapura River. A observasional analitic with a cross-sectional study was conducted among 75 hypertensive patients as research subjects. The independent variable was the level of mercury in blood, and the dependent variables were blood pressure and kidney function. The data results were tested statistically using the Spearman correlation test with 95% confidence level; significance < 0.05. The major finding all blood samples contained

mean mercury level was 3.50 ug/dl, the mean BP of the stage 1 hypertension was 158/98 mmHg and mean BP for stage 2 hypertension was 165/99 mmHg, mean urea level was 2.51 mg/dl, and mean creatinine level was 0.70 mg/dl. There was significant correlation between mercury levels and stage hypetension ($p=0.0385$) and significant correlation between mercury levels and creatinine levels ($p=0.022$). Conclusions the presence of mercury has the potential to worsen progression of hypertension and kidney function in hypertensive patients exposed by the Martapura River. Nurses need to play a role in providing information to relevant institutions about the dangers of mercury pollution in the Martapura River and providing counseling and education to the community.

Keywords: mercury; stage hypertension; renal fuction

Se ha reportado mercurio contaminado en aguas del río Martapura. El mercurio tiene altos niveles de toxicidad para casi todos los órganos, incluidos los sistemas renocardiovasculares y la hipertensión, que es una de las partes de la enfermedad. El objetivo principal del estudio es investigar el efecto del mercurio en el empeoramiento de los resultados de hipertensión en pacientes hipertensos expuestos a la contaminación del río Martapura. Se realizó un estudio analítico observacional con sección transversal entre 75 pacientes hipertensos como sujetos de investigación. La variable independiente era el nivel de mercurio en sangre, y las variables dependientes eran la presión arterial y la función renal. Los resultados de los datos se evaluaron estadísticamente mediante la prueba de correlación de Spearman con un nivel de confianza del 95%; significado < 0,05. El hallazgo principal fue que todas las muestras de sangre contenían el nivel medio de mercurio fue de 3,50 ug/dl, la presión arterial media de la hipertensión en estadio 1 fue de 158/98 mmHg y la presión arterial media para hipertensión en estadio 2 fue de 165/99 mmHg, el nivel medio de urea fue de 2,51 mg/dl y el nivel medio de creatinina fue de 0,70 mg/dl. Hubo una correlación significativa entre los niveles de mercurio y la hipertensión de etapa ($p=0,0385$) y una correlación significativa entre los niveles de mercurio y los niveles de creatinina ($p=0,022$). Conclusiones: **la presencia de mercurio tiene el potencial de empeorar la progresión de la hipertensión y la función renal en pacientes hipertensos expuestos al río Martapura.** Las enfermeras deben desempeñar un papel proporcionando información a las instituciones pertinentes sobre los peligros de la contaminación por mercurio en el río Martapura, así como proporcionando asesoramiento y educación a la comunidad.

Palabras clave: mercurio; hipertensión en estadio ; función renal

Human activities are a major contributor to the emergence of heavy metal contamination and cause environmental changes and ecological imbalances. Most of these environmental contaminations come from the use of metals and metal compounds in the household environment, pharmaceutical sector, industry, food production, and agriculture^{1,2}. The Barito River and its river flows in South Kalimantan have been polluted by heavy metals due to mining and other activities. The type of heavy metal found in the Barito watershed is mercury and is indicated to contaminate the water and the living biota in it.³⁻⁶. The existence of the river is very important for the activities of the Banjar people who have a cultural culture attached to the river. If this condition continues, it will gradually affect the individual's health condition. Martapura River water has also been reported to cause histomorphological changes in the liver, kidneys and testes of rats.⁷⁻⁹ The degree of toxicity shown by heavy metals depends on the number and length of time living organisms are exposed to them. Mercury heavy metals are reported to have high levels of toxicity, carcinogenic, and cause damage to several organs.¹⁰⁻¹². Almost all organ systems are affected by heavy metal toxicity, but the most commonly affected systems are the central nervous system, peripheral nervous system, digestive, hematopoietic, genitourinary, and cardiovascular systems^{2,13}. A number of studies have reported correlations mercury and diseases including the incidence of endocrine metabolic syndrome¹⁴, cardiovascular disease¹⁵⁻¹⁸, carcinogenic^{2,19}, and kidney disorders²⁰⁻²³. Hypertension is a cardiovascular disease that has become a global health problem that leads to renocardiovascular diseases around the world, including residents on the banks of the Martapura river, one of which is in West Martapura district. Hypertension ranks 1st in the 10 most common diseases in 2024 in West Martapura district²⁴. Hypertension is a multifactorial disease whose cause is impaired kidney function. The kidneys are one of the organs susceptible to heavy metal toxicity. Studies have been conducted on the impact of mercury on other researchers^{11,25} as well as previous prospective researchers on liver and kidney function^{26,27}. However, a special study for hypertension patients living along of the Martapura River indicated that exposure to river water contaminated with mercury has never been carried out, so a study is needed to obtain data on mercury blood level caused worsen hypertension and kidney function.

Research design

The study used an observational analytical method with a cross-sectional approach. The research subjects were controlled hypertension patients at the Martapura Barat 's Public Health Center which living in Martapura Barat sub-district and had used Martapura river water (>5 years) for daily needs and were willing to be the subject of the research (signature on the informed consent sheet). The number of research samples obtained was 75 subject.

Measurement and data collection

Mercury in blood sampel examination using AAS (Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy) and examination of kidney function (urea and creatinine) using the Vis spectrophotometry method using blood samples of the study subjects. The blood collection process and blood sample examination were carried out by the Prodia Medical Lab Banjarbaru branch while the identification of the research subjects was carried out in collaboration with nurses at the Martapura Barat's Public Health Center.

Patients are then grouped into 3 categories of hypertension according to WHO, namely:

- Prehypertension : 120-139/80-90 mmHg
- Stage 1 hypertension : 140-159/90-99 mmHg
- Stage 2 hypertension : > 160 / > 100 mmHg

Data analysis

The data obtained from the results of the examination will be included in a table and grouped based on the research variables of mercury levels, urea and creatinine levels and blood pressure. The study-bound variable was the mercury metal content while the independent variable was blood pressure and kidney function. The results of the examination from the examination of blood samples and blood pressure are used to group patients into the following categories based on WHO rules:

- a. Mercury level in human blood (ug/L)
 - Normal : < 10
 - Abnormal : ≥ 10

Urea levels in the blood (mg/dl)

- Normal : < 4,3
- Abnormal : $\geq 4,3$

Creatinine levels in the blood (mg/dl)

- Normal : < 0,9
- Abnormal : $\geq 0,9$

Classification of hypertension

- Prehypertension : 120-139/80-90 mmHg
- Stage 1 Hypertension : 140-159/90-99 mmHg
- Stage 2 hypertension: > 160 / > 100 mmHg

SPSS 25.0 statistical software This study used Spearman's colleration test to analyze correlation between mercury level, blood pressure and kidney function (creatinin and urea level) with confident level 95%; **P-values > 0.05 indicated statistical significance.**

Ethical considerations.

This research has passed the ethics review conducted by the FKIK ULM Health Research Ethics Committee with ethics approval number No.066/KEPK-FKIK ULM/EC/VI/2025

Based on the results of data collection on 75 research subjects , the following results were obtained:

Table 1. Data of Research Subjects

Data	N
Age (year)	54,5±14,05
Blood Pressure (mmHg)	154,5±14,05 (stage 1) 165/99± 163/97(stage 2)
Stage Hypertension	36 patient (stage 1) 39 patient (stage 2)
Ureum level (mg/dl)	25,1±2,53
Creatinin level (mg/dl)	0,70±0,10
Mercury level (ug/L)	3,86±2,67

Note: stage 1 Hypertension : 140-159/90-99 mmHg and Stage 2 hypertension: > 160 / > 100 mmHg; normal creatinine levels in adult : 0.6–1.2 mg/dL; normal urea levels (6–24 mg/dL); permissible mercury levels in blood < 10 Ug/L

From the observation results of Table 1, it was found the average subject ages are 54,5 years, the mean BP of the stage 1 hypertension was 158/98 mmHg and the mean BP for stage 2 hypertension was 165/99 mmHg. The most common patients are those with stage 2 hypertension. The average level of mercury is 3,50 ug/L was normal level; the creatinine level and urea level are still normal.

Table 2. Results of Correlation Analysis between Mercury Level and Stage Hypertension

Mercury Levels	Stage Hypertension		P value
	Stage 1 Hypertension	Stage 2 Hypertension	
Normal	25	19	0,0385*
Abnormal	11	20	
	36	39	

Note: * $p < 0.05$ (significant); Spearman's Colleration Test

In table 2, the following is found there is significant colleration was found between mercury levels and stage hypertension ($p=0.0385$) also there is a tendency that ab-

normal mercury levels are more occurrence in patients with stage 2 hypertension than in patients with stage 1 hypertension.

Table 3. Results of Correlation Analysis between of Mercury and Urea Level

Mercury Level	Ureum level		P Value
	Normal	Abnormal	
Normal	44	0	0,826
Abnormal	31	0	
Total	75	0	

Note: * $p < 0,05$ = significanty ; Spearman's Colleration

In table 3, founds that urea levels in all blood samples sample were still within normal level and there was no significant colleration between mercury levels and blood urea levels ($p=0.826$).

Table 4. Results of Correlation Analysis between Mercury and Creatinine Level

Mercury Levels in Blood Samples	Creatinine Level		P value
	Normal	Abnormal	
Normal	23	21	0,022*
Abnormal	10	21	
Total	33	42	

Note : * $p < 0.05$ (significant); Spearmans Colleration

In table 4, the following is found the presence of mercury in the blood tends to increase creatinine levels . We also found significant colleration between mercury and blood creatinine levels ($p=0.022$)

Hheavy metals are natural components found in the earth's crust that cannot be degraded or destroyed and are dangerous substances because bioaccumulation can occur. Bioaccumulation is an increase in the concentration of chemical substances in the body of living things for a long time, compared to the concentration of chemical substances found in nature. Mercury are reported to have high levels of toxicity and cause damage to several organs. Almost all organ systems are affected by heavy metal toxicity, but the most commonly affected systems are the central nervous system, peripheral nervous system, digestive, hematopoietic, genitourinary, and cardiovascular systems. A number of studies have reported correlations between all three heavy metals and diseases including cardiovascular events and kidney disorders^{26,28-30}. The findings of the study showed all subject had mercury in their blood. The presence of these heavy metals causes a tendency to increase the severity of hypertension through the classification indicators of hypertension and kidney injury (measurement creatinine levels).

From this study, it was found that mercury levels were still within the permissible limit in human blood accord-

ing to WHO (less than 10-15 ng/mL or $\mu\text{g/L}$). However, because the ability of heavy metals have a bioaccumulation effect in cells, in this study it was found that there is a relationship between the incidence of hypertension and the severity of the degree of hypertension accompanied by disturbances in kidney function. It is known that the people of West Martapura have a habit of carrying out their daily domestic activities in the Martapura River. This custom has been passed down from the ancestors of the Banjar people and is very difficult to change. They are unaware that this custom has a negative impact on their health. The public is unaware that mercury contamination has accidentally entered their bodies. Moreover, the mining industry in South Kalimantan has been around for a long time and has not been strictly supervised, so mercury pollution is inevitable.

The toxicity of mercury as a heavy metal from its ability to non-degradable and easily absorbed by living organisms in the environment so that made mercury can accumulate into the environment, mainly depositing on the bottom of the water and forming complex compounds along with organic and inorganic matter. In humans, the occurrence of accidental exposure to heavy metals through ingestion, skin, inhalation, etc^{2,27,31-33}. Studies have linked the occurrence of organ toxicity due to heavy metals due to oxidative stress and the formation of ROS due to the binding of heavy metals to DNA and nuclear proteins. Due to its high level of toxicity, even at lower levels of exposure.^{27,34}

Mercury causes damage to blood vessels, which leads to hypertension through the following mechanisms: (1) Endothelial damage and oxidative stress; Heavy metals can build up on the walls of blood vessels and cause damage to endothelial cells, which are the thin layers that line the inside of blood vessels. This triggers oxidative stress and inflammatory responses, causing blood vessels to become stiffer and less elastic (2) Dysfunction of smooth muscle cells: Damage to the endothelium triggers increased oxidative stress and affects smooth muscle cells in the walls of blood vessels. This causes the smooth muscles to narrow abnormally, reduce the diameter of the blood vessels, and ultimately increase blood pressure (3) Hormonal imbalance disorders: Heavy metals can interfere with the functioning of the endocrine system, including the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone (RAAS) system. This disorder can lead to higher hormone production, which can increase blood pressure³⁵⁻³⁷

The toxicity of mercury is related to its high affinity to sulfhydryl (-SH) groups, forming a stable complex and causing several changes, such as structural changes in the enzyme and inactivating its active sites. Therefore, the binding of mercury to the -SH group of antioxidants, e.g. glutathione (GSH) leads to a reduction in the neutralization capacity of reactive species. Decreased antioxidant defenses coupled with increased levels of reactive species result in an imbalance in the pro-oxidant/an-

ti oxidant system, resulting in oxidative stress conditions.^{38,39} *In vivo* studies and *in vitro* studies have shown that mercury is able to induce inflammation. Several investigations have indicated a role of mercury in pathogenesis related to dyslipidemia, hypertension, insulin resistance, and obesity¹⁷. HgCl toxicity, which has been reported as a nephrotoxic agent through disturbances in kidney function in Wistar mice injected with subcutaneous HgCl₂ (5 mg/kg).⁴⁰

The overall cardiovascular effects of mercury include oxidative stress – decreased oxidative defenses, inflammation, thrombosis, proliferation and migration of vascular smooth muscles, decreased bioavailability of NO, dyslipidemia, and dysfunction of the immune, endothelial, and mitochondrial systems.⁴¹ Mercury exposure increases the production of free radicals and ROS and increases the risk of developing cardiovascular disease. In addition, Hg has the potential to affect phospholipase and increase LDL (low-density lipoprotein) oxidation. Another mechanism responsible for the toxic effects of mercury is the inactivation of paraoxonase, an extracellular antioxidant enzyme associated with HDL (high-density lipoprotein), which causes HDL to be dysfunctional to reduce reverse cholesterol transport and reduce LDL antioxidant activity. This process is directly involved in the development of atherosclerosis and the risk of acute myocardial infarction, coronary heart disease, and carotid artery stenosis. In addition, mercury induces the formation of arachidonic acid metabolites, such as prostaglandins, thromboxans, leukotrienes, and related compounds, all of which are thought to mediate inflammatory responses that may be associated with cardiovascular problems.^{1,17,42,43}

From a nursing perspective, these findings emphasize the critical need for comprehensive environmental health assessments as part of routine clinical evaluations in endemic areas. Nurses should be aware that patients from polluted environments may have a complex history of exposure that affects disease presentation and response to treatment. The findings of this study have several important implications for the care of hypertensive patients in polluted environments, namely: (1) Comprehensive nursing monitoring assessments should include environmental exposure history, especially for patients from areas with known contamination. Routine monitoring of blood pressure and kidney function parameters is essential for early detection of disease progression (2) Patient education on the importance of preventing environmental pollution and the risks of mercury contamination on the health of hypertensive patients. For riverside communities, information on alternative water sources and safe practices to minimize mercury ingestion can be added (3) Interdisciplinary collaboration in the management of hypertensive patients affected by environmental contamination, such as cross-disciplinary collaboration including nephrology, cardiology, public health, and environmental health experts (4) These findings support

the need for community-level interventions that address upstream health determinants in contaminated areas. Public health nursing initiatives may include screening programs, health education campaigns, and advocacy for environmental remediation (5) Systematically document environmental exposure information to contribute to the occupational and environmental health evidence base. This documentation supports both individual patient care and population health research^{44–46}.

Conclusions

The presence of mercury has toxic potential to cause changes in blood pressure and kidney function in patients with hypertension in West Martapura district. The results found that heavy metal mercury pollution can affect the health of patients with hypertension. Therefore, nurses need to play a role in providing information to relevant institutions about the dangers of mercury pollution in the Martapura River and providing counseling and education to the community, especially patients with hypertension, to continue regular treatment to prevent their condition from worsening. In terms of science, it is also necessary to conduct Further research is needed to investigate the molecular mechanisms underlying organ damage such as endothelial vascular dysfunction, dysfunction of smooth muscle cells, and imbalance hormonal due to mercury contamination, such as measuring levels of oxidative stress biomarkers, markers of inflammatory processes and cellular signal transduction pathways.

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Conflict of interest

None

1. Lamas GA, Bhatnagar A, Jones MR, Mann KK, Nasir K, Tellez-Plaza M, et al. Contaminant Metals as Cardiovascular Risk Factors: A Scientific Statement From the American Heart Association. *J Am Heart Assoc.* 2023;12(13):1–17.
2. Balali-Mood M, Naseri K, Tahergorabi Z, Khazdair MR, Sadeghi M. Toxic mechanisms of five heavy metals: mercury, lead, chromium, cadmium, and arsenic. *Front Pharmacol.* 2021;12(April):1–19.
3. Rahmadani; Alawiyah T. Deteksi Logam Berat (Hg) pada Air dan Ikan Pasca Pertambangan Emas di Sungai Barito kabupaten Barito Utara. *J Surya Med.* 2022;8(3):76–80.
4. Zubaidah T, Karnaningroem N, Slamet A, Ratodi M. Pollution Load Capacity Study on Barito River, South Kalimantan, Indonesia. Preprint. 2018;(February):1–9.
5. Herliwati, Rahman M, Hidayat AS, Amri U, Sumantri I. The Occurrences of Heavy Metals in Water, Sediment and Wild Shrimps Caught from Barito Estuary, South Kalimantan, Indonesia. *HAYATI J Biosci.* 2022;29(5):643–7.
6. Wibowo MA, Rahman M, Mahyudin I, Fatmawati D, Lambung U, Banjarbaru M. ANALISIS LOGAM BERAT (Mn,Pb,Cu,Fe) PADA AIR. *EnviroScienteeae.* 2022;18(2):100–5.
7. Yuliana I, Khatimah H, Rosida L, Skripsiana NS, Suhartono E. Martapura river water leads to testes alteration in rats. *J Phys Conf Ser.* 2019;1374(1).
8. Yuliana I, Prenggono MD, Oktavianti IK, Ulfah F. The Effects of Heavy Metal Contamination on Liver Function in a Rat Model. *MAGNA MEDICA Berk Ilm Kedokt dan Kesehat.* 2024;11(August):145–53.
9. Rana MN, Tangpong J, Rahman MM. Toxicodynamics of Lead, Cadmium, Mercury and Arsenic- induced kidney toxicity and treatment strategy: A mini review. *Toxicol Reports* [Internet]. 2018;5(April):704–13. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxrep.2018.05.012>
10. Abd Elnabi MK, Elkaliny NE, Elyazied MM, Azab SH, Elkhailifa SA, Elmasry S, et al. Toxicity of Heavy Metals and Recent Advances in Their Removal: A Review. *Toxics.* 2023;11(7).
11. Gao Z, Wu N, Du X, Li H, Mei X, Song Y. Toxic Nephropathy Secondary to Chronic Mercury Poisoning: Clinical Characteristics and Outcomes. *Kidney Int Reports.* 2022;7(6):1189–97.
12. Yin G, Zhao S, Zhao M, Xu J, Ge X, Wu J, et al. Complex interplay of heavy metals and renal injury: New perspectives from longitudinal epidemiological evidence. *Ecotoxicol Environ Saf* [Internet]. 2024;278(February):116424. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2024.116424>
13. Han B, Lv Z, Han X, Li S, Han B, Yang Q, et al. Harmful Effects of Inorganic Mercury Exposure on Kidney Cells: Mitochondrial Dynamics Disorder and Excessive Oxidative Stress. *Biol Trace Elem Res.* 2022 Apr;200(4):1591–7.
14. Tinkov AA, Ajsuvakova OP, Skalnaya MG, Popova E V., Sinitkii AI, Nemereshina ON, et al. Mercury and metabolic syndrome: A review of experimental and clinical observations. *BioMetals.* 2015;28(2):231–54.
15. Sumaily KM. The Roles and Pathogenesis Mechanisms of a Number of Micronutrients in the Prevention and/or Treatment of Chronic Hepatitis, COVID-19 and Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus. *Nutrients.* 2022;14(13).
16. Shetty SS, D D, S H, Sonkusare S, Naik PB, Kumari N S, et al. Environmental pollutants and their effects on human health. *Heliyon* [Internet]. 2023;9(9):e19496. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e19496>
17. Haidar Z, Fatema K, Shoily SS, Sajib AA. Disease-associated metabolic pathways affected by heavy metals and metalloids. *Toxicol Reports* [Internet]. 2023;10(January):554–70. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxrep.2023.04.010>
18. Khaydarova B. The Association between ambient air pollution and resistant hypertensive disorders in pregnancy: a case-control study in Tashkent.
19. Negahdari S, Sabaghan M, Pirhadi M, Alikord M, Sadighara P, Darvishi M, et al. Potential Harmful Effects of Heavy Metals as a Toxic and Carcinogenic Agent in Marine Food-An Overview. *Egypt J Vet Sci.* 2021;52(3):379–85.
20. Vieira JV dos A, Marques VB, Vieira LV, Crajoins R de O, Shimizu MHM, Seguro AC, et al. Changes in the renal function after acute mercuric chloride exposure in the rat are associated with renal vascular endothelial dysfunction and proximal tubule NHE3 inhibition. *Toxicol Lett.* 2021;341:23–32.
21. Moumen Y, Malki S, Bensaas F, Belaloui M, Boudjerar Z, Ferag D. The protective role of virgin olive oil and vitamin E on mercury-induced hepatic, renal, testicular and adrenal toxicity in the rabbit (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*). *Acta Vet Brno.* 2024;93(2):183–99.
22. Kouam AF, Masso M, Kouoh FE, Fifen R, Njingou I, Tchana AN, et al. Hydro-ethanolic extract of *Khaya grandifoliola* attenuates heavy metals-induced hepato-renal injury in rats by reducing oxidative stress and metals-bioaccumulation. *Heliyon.* 2022;8(11).
23. Ida, Yuliana Ida, Triawanti, M Darwin Prenggono IKO, Maulana I, Prenggono MD, Oktavianti IK, Kania N, et al. Mercury exposure triggers diabetes mellitus through a pancreatic beta cell endoplasmic reticulum stress mechanism. *Rev Latinoam Hipertens.* 2025;20(6).
24. Resume Profil Kesehatan UPTD Puskesmas Martapura Barat Tahun 2023. 2023.
25. Javid A, Akbar I, Javed H, Khan U, Iftikhar H, Zahra D, et al. Role of Heavy Metals in Diabetes: Mechanisms and Treatment Strategies. *Crit Rev Eukaryot Gene Expr* [Internet]. 2021;31(3):65–80. Available from: <http://www.dl.begellhouse.com/journals/6dbf508d3b17c437,276309ca23c68a1c,3ecf1e6e4170aff4.html>
26. Barregard L, Sallsten G, Lundh T, Mölne J. Low-level exposure to lead, cadmium and mercury, and histopathological findings in kidney biopsies. *Environ Res.* 2022;211(December 2021).
27. Godwill Aزه Engwa PUF, Unachukwu FNN and MN. Mechanism and health effects of heavy metal toxicity in humans. *Intechopen* [Internet]. 2019;11(tourism):13. Available from: <https://www.intechopen.com/books/advanced-biometric-technologies/liveness-detection-in-biometrics>
28. Riaz MA, Nisa ZU, Anjum MS, Butt H, Mehmood A, Riaz A, et al. Assessment of metals induced histopathological and gene expression changes in different organs of non-diabetic and diabetic rats. *Sci Rep* [Internet]. 2020;10(1):1–11. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-62807-0>
29. Ezejiofor AN, Orish CN, Akaranta O. Multi-Organ induced toxicity of metal mixture (CdCl₂, HgCl₂, Pb(NO₃)), and the ameliorative potentials of plantain *Musa paradisiaca* (F. Musaceae) stem juice on male Wistar rats. *Int J Physiol Pathophysiol Pharmacol* [Internet]. 2022;14(4):211–24. Available from: <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/36161263> <http://www.pubmedcentral.nih.gov/articlerender.fcgi?artid=PMC9490206>

30. Mishra M, Nichols L, Dave AA, Pittman EH, Cheek JP, Caroland AJV, et al. Molecular Mechanisms of Cellular Injury and Role of Toxic Heavy Metals in Chronic Kidney Disease. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2022;23(19).
31. Cortés S, Zúñiga-Venegas L, Pancetti F, Covarrubias A, Ramírez-Santana M, Adaros H, et al. A positive relationship between exposure to heavy metals and development of chronic diseases: A case study from Chile. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2021;18(4):1–13.
32. Sevim Ç, Doğan E, Comakli S. Cardiovascular disease and toxic metals. *Curr Opin Toxicol*. 2020;19:88–92.
33. Kang B, Wang J, Guo S, Yang L. Mercury-induced toxicity: Mechanisms, molecular pathways, and gene regulation. *Sci Total Environ* [Internet]. 2024 Sep;943:173577. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0048969724037240>
34. Zheng F, Gonçalves FM, Abiko Y, Li H, Kumagai Y, Aschner M. Redox toxicology of environmental chemicals causing oxidative stress. *Redox Biol* [Internet]. 2020;34(December 2019):101475. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.redox.2020.101475>
35. Aguado A, Galán M, Zhenyukh O, Wiggers GA, Roque FR, Redondo S, et al. Mercury induces proliferation and reduces cell size in vascular smooth muscle cells through MAPK, oxidative stress and cyclooxygenase-2 pathways. *Toxicol Appl Pharmacol* [Internet]. 2013;268(2):188–200. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.taap.2013.01.030>
36. Meyer BA, Doroudgar S. ER Stress-Induced Secretion of Proteins and Their Extracellular Functions in the Heart. *Cells*. 2020;9(9):1–17.
37. Wu YS, Osman AI, Hosny M, Elgarahy AM, Eltaweil AS, Rooney DW, et al. The Toxicity of Mercury and Its Chemical Compounds: Molecular Mechanisms and Environmental and Human Health Implications: A Comprehensive Review. *ACS Omega*. 2024;9(5):5100–26.
38. Ciacci C, Betti M, Abramovich S, Cavaliere M, Frontalini F. Mercury-induced oxidative stress response in benthic foraminifera: An in vivo experiment on *Ammonia lessona*. *Biology (Basel)*. 2022;11(7):1–12.
39. Al Doghaither H, Elmorsy E, Al-Ghafari A, Ghulam J. Roles of oxidative stress, apoptosis, and inflammation in metal-induced dysfunction of beta pancreatic cells isolated from CD1 mice. *Saudi J Biol Sci* [Internet]. 2021;28(1):651–63. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sjbs.2020.10.056>
40. Vig S, Lambooj JM, Zaldumbide A, Guigas B. Endoplasmic Reticulum-Mitochondria Crosstalk and Beta-Cell Destruction in Type 1 Diabetes. *Front Immunol*. 2021;12(April):1–10.
41. Axrorov A, Sharipova E, Xamidov N, Yunusov D, Ikramova N, Furkatjon A, et al. pigenetic clocks and biological aging acceleration in early-onset hypertension. 2026;21.
42. An J, Nichols GA, Qian L, Munis MA, Harrison TN, Li Z, et al. Prevalence and incidence of microvascular and macrovascular complications over 15 years among patients with incident type 2 diabetes. *BMJ Open Diabetes Res Care*. 2021;9(1):1–10.
43. Dilbar K, Visola G, Nodirjon K, Dildora K, Sukhrob K, Ismoilov J, et al. Immunosenescence and inflammaging: mechanistic contributions to geriatric hypertension 52. 1984;
44. Arooj H, Aman M, Hashmi MU, Nasir Z, Zahid M, Abbas J. The impact of nurse - led care in chronic kidney disease management : a systematic review and meta - analysis. *BMC Nurs* [Internet]. 2025; Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-025-02829-z>
45. Sibindi T, Chipps J, Anne, Crowley T. *International Journal of Nursing Studies Advances Eco-nursing competencies for nurses : A scoping review*. *Int J Nurs Stud Adv* [Internet]. 2024;7(October 2023):100221. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnnsa.2024.100221>
46. Nurhadijah S, Zamaa MS, Harun B, Sahida M. Environmental nursing practices as a solution for reducing exposure to environmental hazards. 2025;2(1):31–51.